
Council
ON
Library
AND
Information
Resources

Annual Report 2007–2008

DIRECTORS, JULY 1, 2007–JUNE 30, 2008

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2007–2008

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University of California, Irvine	University of Nebraska-Lincoln	Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
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University of Cincinnati	University of Oregon	Wesleyan University
University of Colorado at Boulder	University of Pennsylvania	Wheaton College
University of Connecticut	University of Pittsburgh	Whitman College
University of Delaware Library	University of Richmond	Williams College Libraries
	University of Rochester	Yale University

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(as of June 30, 2008)

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Cummins-Allison Corporation	Howard and Mathilde Rovelstad	National Endowment for the Humanities
Documentation Abstracts, Inc.	Institute for Library and Information Services	Robert W. Woodruff Foundation

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(AS OF JUNE 30, 2008)

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Bryn Mawr College

LETTER FROM THE CHAIRPERSON

Paula Kaufman
Chairman of the Board

As we all face turbulent economic times, CLIR is stepping up its important role in helping us and our institutions look forward to shape the opportunities and challenges that lie ahead. As this annual report attests, CLIR has made significant progress toward achieving the objectives it set in its ambitious three-year agenda for 2007–2010. Several exciting new efforts are under way in areas relating to cyberinfrastructure, preservation, the transformation of scholarly methodologies, the emerging library, and leadership. The CLIR Board and staff have also taken the opportunity to reflect on how to leverage the results of these efforts so they can add up to more than the sum of their parts.

Developing leaders is one of the most important things we can do, and one of the most significant legacies we leave. CLIR has invested heavily in leadership development—from the Frye Institute to the Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries for Humanists, to the CLIR CIO Group, and the new Hidden Collections Program—that reaches into communities of graduate students, scholars, senior administrators, and library and IT leaders. To leverage these investments, CLIR President Chuck Henry and Presidential Fellow Elliott Shore are developing a “collegium” of these participants to “apply their collective experience and knowledge to real-world challenges and opportunities and to generate new research that will help institutions of higher education address some of the most daunting transformational challenges of the past 150 years.”

CLIR’s work would not be possible without the investments that several funding agencies have made in our vision. This year, CLIR received significant new funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation to support the new Hidden Collections Program and a separate grant to examine the scholarly utility of large-scale digitization projects. CLIR also received new grants from the Institute for Museum and Library Services, Library of Congress, National Endowment for the Humanities, and Samuel H. Kress Foundation.

In November 2008, CLIR will move from its home of the past 11 years to new offices a block south. There will be ample meeting space at the new address, and given the variety of activities planned in the year ahead, there will be plenty of opportunities to visit CLIR in its new location. We look forward to welcoming you!

Paula Kaufman
October 2008

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

It has been a productive year for CLIR. A notable achievement was our establishment of a nationally competitive grant program, “Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives.” The new program, supported by a generous grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, will identify and support the cataloging of hidden unique materials of significant scholarly value. The goals of the program are sweeping. Funded projects must use cataloging methodologies that are broadly applicable and built upon over time. The means of data creation must be cost-effective and efficient; it must also ensure the rapid construction of a critical mass of trustworthy and authoritative information. To meet these criteria, funded projects must be national in scope: scores of institutions and hundreds of graduate students will be involved, as will research faculty and subject experts representing many disciplines and studies. This year may thus be defined by an extension of CLIR’s national presence that will influence the trajectory of our research agenda.

A more encompassing approach to our projects and programs is consonant with the complexity of the challenges before us. CLIR’s constituencies—libraries and librarians, information technologists, researchers and scholars across academic fields—have traditionally been organized by societies and associations that are focused on distinct professional groups and governed by the experience gained within fairly explicit behavioral constructs. Research has been similarly discipline based, roles within higher education have been fairly sharply delineated, and institutions of higher education have traditionally defined themselves in terms that reflect a discrete, local, and congenially idiosyncratic nature.

Much of this has now changed because of transformations in the research process itself. Today, global projects generate terabytes of information annually. There has been a rise in interdisciplinary research, with increasing examples of new methodological approaches facilitated by technologies. The proliferation of digital humanities efforts is a case in point. It is also evident that scholars are now collaborating more closely with librarians and IT experts as integral participants in research projects. Research is becoming more a process and less a product manifested in distinctly bounded iterations. Data compilation, analysis, discovery, publication, and reuse is becoming a more fluid enterprise as the scale of collaboration grows, as institutional repositories and digital libraries increase in number,

and as digital publication platforms allow more opportunity for the social construction of knowledge and pose few limits to revising and reconstituting content.

CLIR has a twofold advantage in this new environment: our constituencies are fluid and interactive, and our remit is by definition broad. In the past year we have begun to explore some of the phenomena noted above and to convene experts and stakeholders to assess and interpret the possible transformations over time. Our efforts include working with allied organizations to ascertain the opportunities and limits imposed by our governance models; identifying mechanisms to develop new skills and expertise to more effectively manage the changes taking place; working with a core group of forward-looking research libraries and universities to discuss prototypes for interinstitutional collaboration on a large scale; convening librarians, faculty members, and IT professionals to explore support skills and systems needed for interdisciplinary, multi-institutional research; studying current policies of assessment and credentialing in a variety of academic programs and professions; and seeking funding for leadership and training for the next generation of research faculty and librarians.

An assumption underlying much of this activity is that no single profession, organization, or institution can address the transforming environment in ways that are genuinely cost-effective and efficient. New alliances and coalitions are required, as are new concepts of organization, and perhaps new professions, to best respond to the need for vibrant and elastic reformulations that characterize the 21st century.

Charles Henry

October 2008

THE PROGRAMS

CLIR undertook the following programmatic work between July 1, 2007, and June 30, 2008.

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives: Building a New Research Environment

Libraries, archives, and cultural institutions hold millions of items that have never been adequately described. These items are all but unknown to, and unused by, the scholars those organizations aim to serve. In March 2008, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded CLIR \$4.27 million to create a national program to identify and catalog hidden special collections and archives. The program will award funds to institutions holding collections of high scholarly value that are difficult or impossible to locate through finding aids. Award recipients will create descriptive information for their hidden collections that will be linked to and interoperable with that of all other projects funded by this grant. In so doing, they will create a federated environment that can be built upon over time.

CLIR envisions engaging both postdoctoral scholars and graduate students in this program—the former to observe and advise; the latter, hired by grantee institutions, to assist with the generation of records. The aim is to build a stable community of students who are either participating or interested in this program.

In conjunction with the hidden collections program, CLIR commissioned Lisa Spiro, director of the Digital Media Center at Rice University, to examine existing archival management systems and tools for creating and publishing EAD finding aids. Her report, which will be published late in 2008, will provide a basis upon which to build from the experiences of institutions that receive funds in 2008. Spiro is also building a wiki that will support ongoing discussions and comment.

Digital Humanities Centers

Study of Digital Humanities Centers. In 2007, CLIR commissioned information management consultant Diane Zorich to conduct a survey of some 30 U.S.-based digital humanities centers (DHCs)—entities “where new

media and technologies are used for humanities-based research, teaching, and intellectual engagement and experimentation.” The survey investigated the scope, financing, organizational structure, products, services, financing, and sustainability of DHCs, as well as the collaborative aspects of existing models. Completed in May 2008, the survey was used to inform Scholarly Communications Institute 6 (SCI 6), held in June at the University of Virginia. SCI 6 was devoted to assessing the needs, priorities, and challenges of national DHCs.

Survey of Digital Humanities Tools. Digital tools—software or computing products developed to provide access to, interpret, create, or communicate digital resources—are a critical part of the cyberinfrastructure that supports digital humanities research. Such tools are increasingly developed and supported by DHCs and the wider digital humanities community. However, the accessibility and clarity of these tools vary. If they are not visible, accessible, or understandable to researchers, they are less likely to be used broadly, less able to be built upon or extended, and ultimately less able to support the research for which they are intended.

In October 2007, CLIR commissioned Lilly Nguyen and Katie Shilton, graduate students in the Department of Information Studies at the University of California, Los Angeles, to evaluate 39 tools developed by DHCs surveyed in Diane Zorich’s report. Specifically, they looked at the clarity of intentions and functions of the tools and the ease with which users can access them.

Nguyen’s and Shilton’s findings are included as an appendix to the study of DHCs, which CLIR will publish in November 2008.

Promoting Digital Scholarship: Building the Environment

In November 2007, CLIR hosted an invitational workshop to discuss how very large digital collections are changing humanities research, and what infrastructure or systems are needed to provide services and materials to scholars who are dealing with collections on a new, and vastly expanded, scale. Attendees at the workshop, which was cochaired by Tufts University Professor of Classics Gregory Crane and CLIR Director of Programs Amy Friedlander, included scholars in the digital humanities and representatives of research and funding agencies. A meeting report, *Many More than a Million: Building the Digital Environment for the Age of Abundance*, issued in March 2008, includes a summary of the discussions and identifies priorities for future work. It is available at <http://www.clir.org/activities/digitalscholar/index.html>.

Promoting Digital Scholarship: Formulating Research Challenges in the Humanities, Social Sciences and Computation

In December 2007, the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) and CLIR launched a collaborative effort to develop a workshop to identify long-term research challenges at the intersection of humanities, social sciences, and computation. The impetus for the workshop was the recognition that digital humanists increasingly face problems of organizing, engineering, and deploying the technologies they need to operate at a very large scale. Some 30 leading scholars, technologists, and foundation representatives attended the workshop, held in September 2008. To frame the discussions, CLIR commissioned a series of background papers illustrating the kinds of research projects that are possible and that point to future needs in areas such as archiving and preservation, data analysis, and semantic tools. CLIR will publish these papers, along with a summary of workshop discussions, early in 2009.

Seamless Cyberinfrastructure

In recent years, academic libraries have launched major initiatives to make their resources more easily available to users, but it often difficult to know who is using these new resources and how well are they meeting users' needs. In August 2007, CLIR commissioned Dawn Schmitz to write a report that examines who is, or may be, using institutional repositories and mass-digitized collections and outlines steps that academic and research libraries can take to learn more about them. The report is based on the premise that the most successful projects are those that are most widely used, and that understanding how resources are used, and by whom, will lead to initiatives that will earn a secure place among funding priorities. The report suggests strategies that libraries may use to enhance the long-term planning and design of these projects. It is available at www.clir.org/pubs/archives/schmitz.pdf.

Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access

Along with the Library of Congress, the National Archives and Records Administration, and the Joint Information Systems Committee of the United Kingdom, CLIR is an institutional participant in the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access. The task force, created in September 2007, is funded by the National Science Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

The task force is charged with developing recommendations for promoting the economic sustainability of digital information for the academic, public, and private sectors. It is cochaired by Fran Berman, director of the San Diego Supercomputer Center at the University of California, San Diego, and Brian Lavoie, research scientist and economist in the Office

of Research of the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, Inc. The task force's 17 members represent a cross-section of fields and disciplines, including information and computer sciences, economics, entertainment, library and archival sciences, government, and business. The group held its first meeting in Washington, D.C., January 29–30, 2008.

Over the course of its work, the task force will produce a series of articles about the challenges and opportunities of digital information preservation for both the scholarly community and the public. Its final report will include an analysis of issues and recommendations for catalyzing the development of sustainable resource strategies for the preservation of digital information. More information about the Blue Ribbon Task Force can be found at <http://brtf.sdsc.edu>.

National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program

CLIR continues to provide research and editing support for the Library of Congress' National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program. This included editing early drafts of the Section 108 report, which addresses proposed revisions of the Digital Millennium Copyright Act to take into account the exceptions for libraries, archives, and museums in the context of networked, electronic information; a series of confidential interviews with key figures on the topics of e-journals, Web sites, broadcast television, and geographical information systems; and substantial support for the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access. The Library's support has enabled CLIR to hire an intern, Lorraine Eakin, who has completed her doctoral coursework in the School of Library and Information Science at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Ms. Eakin holds undergraduate and masters' degrees in economics, and she has pursued doctoral-level studies in economics at the University of Chicago. Her area of dissertation research will be information and the economics of preservation.

Preservation in the Age of Large-Scale Digitization: A White Paper

In February 2008, CLIR published a report that examines large-scale digital initiatives to identify issues that will influence the availability and usability, over time, of the digital books such projects create. Oya Y. Rieger, associate university librarian for information technologies at Cornell University Library, wrote the report, which is available at www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub141abst.html.

The paper describes four large-scale projects—Google Book Search, Microsoft Live Search Books (now defunct), Open Content Alliance, and the Million Book Project—and their digitization strategies. It then discusses a range of issues affecting the stewardship of the digital collections they create: selection, quality in content creation, technical infrastructure, and

organizational infrastructure. The paper also attempts to foresee the likely impacts of large-scale digitization on book collections.

Analysis of the Effects of Mass Digitization on Scholarship

In July 2007, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded funds to CLIR and Georgetown University to assess selected large-scale digitization programs by exploring their efficacy and utility for conducting scholarship in a variety of disciplines. Scholars were commissioned to conduct research using these large data sets, to write reports summarizing the results of their projects, and to make recommendations for improving the design of the mass digitization projects as well as for future development of a burgeoning digital text environment.

In 2009, CLIR will convene a meeting at which scholars who have reviewed the reports discuss recommendations, assumptions, and next steps. Following this meeting, CLIR will create a collegium of scholars to serve as an advisory group that can collaborate with corporations involved in mass digitization to help assure the highest quality of data and the highest level of utility.

Reconceiving Research Libraries in the 21st Century

In February 2008, CLIR convened 25 leading librarians, publishers, faculty members, and information technology specialists to consider how we should be rethinking the research library in a swiftly changing information landscape. Participants discussed the challenges and opportunities that libraries are likely to face in the next 5 to 10 years, and how changes in scholarly communication will affect the future library. A key theme of the discussions was that the future of the research library cannot be considered apart from that of the academy as a whole. To inform the discussions, CLIR commissioned and circulated before the meeting essays from eight of the participants, representing, variously, the perspectives of a provost, publisher, historian, foundation representative, librarians, and faculty members. In August 2008, CLIR published a full report of the meeting, including the background essays. It is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub142abst.html>.

Symposium on Scholarly Methods in the Humanities

In April 2008, CLIR and Brown University Libraries cosponsored a Symposium on Scholarly Methods in the Humanities. The symposium was inspired by several questions, including: How has technology transformed teaching and learning? Given the tectonic shifts in every domain of scientific, technical, and artistic practice, what is legitimate scholarship? How is a scholar defined, and by whom, in this new environment? What is the role of the academic library in preserving and providing access to scholarship as well as in promoting the path to new scholarship? How has the academy changed, and how will it continue to change?

Speakers examined the role and impact of multimodal literacies on transforming the student's experience as scholar and lifelong learner. They also explored ways in which technology helps students think like scholars, how it helps students become digital scholars, and how their digital scholarship will ultimately change the definition of disciplines, as well as of scholarship and, ultimately, the academy itself.

EthicShare

EthicShare, a new online research environment, explores novel approaches to facilitating scholarship by taking advantage of social technologies and the expertise of the research communities it seeks to serve. An interdisciplinary and multi-institutional undertaking, EthicShare is developing a research Web site for the practical ethics community that incorporates a database of source materials and tools to enable community interaction and engagement. The project, currently in a pilot stage, addresses many of the challenges researchers face in the 21st century: the overwhelming amount of information available and the difficulty of keeping up with a field, the need to master new areas of research for interdisciplinary projects, and the desire to work collaboratively.

Based at the University of Minnesota and funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation with additional support from CLIR, the EthicShare pilot project grows out of a 2006–07 planning grant from CLIR and the Mellon Foundation. The project is a collaboration between the Center for Bioethics, University Libraries, and Department of Computer Science and Engineering at the University of Minnesota..

More information about EthicShare is available at www.ethicshare.org and www.lib.umn.edu/about/ethicshare.

Faculty Research Behavior Workshops

Early in 2007, CLIR piloted the first of its Faculty Research Behavior Workshops, which teach library and IT professionals ethnographic techniques that enable them to understand faculty members' work practices and how library and information services can address real faculty needs. Led by Nancy Foster, an anthropologist at the University of Rochester, the workshops have rapidly grown in popularity. During the past year, CLIR sponsored workshops at Cornell University (Nov. 5–6); the University of California, Berkeley (Feb. 20–21); and George Washington University (April 28–29).

Robert Slater, Web technologies and content coordinator at the University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign Library, wrote a lively and detailed account of his experience at the April workshop. It is available at <http://caflib.blogspot.com/2008/04/my-notes-from-clir-workshop-on-faculty.html>.

We are prepared to develop a cadre of librarians who have the MLS as well as those who do not in order to obtain the depth in subject expertise that our faculty, researchers, graduate students, and collections really need.

—Susan E. Parker
Deputy University Librarian and CFO
UCLA Library
Host to CLIR Postdoctoral Fellow

2008–09 Fellows in Academic Libraries for Humanists

<i>Fellow</i>	<i>Fellowship Host Institution</i>
Gloria E. Chacon	University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)
Gabrielle N. O. Dean	The Johns Hopkins University
Ernestina Osorio	UCLA
Heather Waldroup	Claremont University Consortium
Susan Wiesner	University of North Carolina, Greensboro

The following fellows will continue their postdoctoral research during the coming year:

Lori Miller	Appalachian College Association
Elizabeth Waraksa	UCLA

2008–09 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Alex Borucki, Emory University
Simonetta Marin, University of Miami
Noah Millstone, Stanford University
Tracy Neumann, New York University
Lata Parwani, Tufts University
Martin Renner, University of California, Santa Cruz
Kellie Warren, Tulane University
Alice Wolfram, Yale University
Winnie Wong, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries for Humanists

CLIR created the Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries for Humanists in response to changes in scholarly communication and the growing need to develop linkages among disciplinary scholarship, libraries, archives, and evolving digital tools.

In June 2008, five humanists were awarded new postdoctoral fellowships for 2008–09; two fellows from the previous cohort are continuing their fellowships. In July, the five new fellows spent two weeks at Bryn Mawr College, where, under the tutelage of CLIR Senior Presidential Fellow Elliott Shore, they learned about the profession of academic librarianship. They met with several leaders in the library and information community to discuss issues affecting the profession. During two days of the seminar, they were joined by their supervisors and several former fellows.

In December 2007, CLIR received a planning grant from the Institute for Museum and Library Services to explore the possibility of giving institutions that have hosted postdoctoral fellows and are engaged in large-scale digitization projects a chance to develop a cohort of humanities and social sciences scholars who will work toward coordinating and linking the new large-scale initiatives that are being developed nationwide. CLIR convened two meetings, one in Washington, D.C., in March, and the other at the University of California, Los Angeles, in June, to develop a model that will build on this program by challenging fellows to solve problems of national as well as local concern.

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

This year, nine graduate students were selected to receive Mellon Dissertation Fellowships. The fellowships are intended to help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue original-source doctoral research and gain skill and creativity in using primary source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories.

Established in 2001 and administered by CLIR, the program has awarded 10–15 annual fellowships of up to \$20,000 each. In spring 2008, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded a grant that will allow CLIR to offer about 15 fellowships each year and increase each to \$25,000. CLIR will award the first round of these new fellowships in 2009.

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute is designed to develop leaders who can guide and transform academic information services for higher education. The institute, which CLIR sponsors with EDUCAUSE and Emory University, is now in its ninth year. It has trained some 400 librarians, faculty members, and IT experts.

Frye Institute Participants Class of 2008

Karen Albert, Fox Chase Cancer Center
Neal Baker, Earlham College
Keith Boswell, North Carolina State University
Joan Cheverie, Georgetown University
Ann Crawford, University of Connecticut School of Law
Trevor Dawes, Princeton University
Lisa DeMings, Brandeis University
Samantha Earp, Duke University
Angi Faiks, Macalester College
James Frazee, San Diego State University
Meg Fryling, University at Albany, SUNY
Jeffrey Gima, AMICAL (American International Consortium of Academic Libraries)
Gillian Gremmels, Davidson College
Laurie Harrison, University of Toronto
Kevin Hundere, Maricopa County Community College District/Glendale Community College
Carol Hunter, University of Virginia
J. Q. Johnson, University of Oregon
Lisa Kemp Jones, University of California, Los Angeles
Deborah Keyek-Franssen, University of Colorado at Boulder
Louis King, University of Michigan
Vivian Lewis, McMaster University Library
Adriene Lim, Portland State University
Felice Maciejewski, St. Norbert College
Maribeth Manoff, University of Tennessee Libraries
Lars Meyer, Emory University
David Middleton, Seton Hall University
Vivian Lewis, George Mason University
Robert Moropa, University of Pretoria
Lesley Moyo, Virginia Tech
Brian Nichols, Louisiana State University A&M College
Nick Noakes, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
Marla Peppers, Occidental College
Gail Persily, University of California, San Francisco
Paul Petersen, Emory University
Anne Posega, Washington University
Jeannette Riley, University of Massachusetts, Dartmouth
Mark Ritschard, Colorado State University
Carlos Rodriguez, California State University, Sacramento
Michael Rubesch, Purdue University
Beth Schaefer, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee
Maureen Scoones, Hamilton College
Sarah Shreeves, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
Elizabeth Siecke, Ramapo College of New Jersey
Scott Silverman, Bryn Mawr College
Bryan Sinclair, University of North Carolina at Asheville
Julie Sweetkind-Singer, Stanford University
Judith Tabron, Hofstra University
Jennifer Vinopal, New York University

The 2008 institute was held June 1–12, 2008, at Emory University in Atlanta, Georgia. The 48 participants came from research universities, master's degree institutions, liberal arts colleges, and community colleges. Two participants came from universities abroad. Susan Perry, former CLIR interim president, and Brian Hawkins, former EDUCAUSE president, served as deans. The Frye Institute is supported with funds from the Robert W. Woodruff Foundation.

Chief Information Officers

CLIR facilitates a semiannual forum that enables chief information officers (CIOs) of merged library computing units in liberal arts colleges to discuss issues affecting teaching and learning on their campuses. At their May 2008 meeting, the CLIR CIOs agreed to host a professional job exchange listserve that will allow their group, the Oberlin Group, the Associated Colleges of Appalachia, the Historically Black Colleges and Universities Library Alliance, and the American International Consortium of Academic Libraries to share expertise by making their needs known and exchanging staff. Exchange participants will work on discrete projects, such as digital asset management, open source software development, or new reference or technical service methods. They will not only share their knowledge with counterparts at the visiting institutions but also convey what they learned from their exchange experience to their colleagues upon returning to their home institutions.

A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management

Meredith Weiss, a doctoral student in information science at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, was selected to receive the 2008 A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management. Weiss's research focuses on higher education technology administration, organizational design, communications and leadership; human computer interaction; user-interface design; information system development and evaluation; and business intelligence systems. Her dissertation examines how chief information officers in institutions of higher education can best use academic evidence to ensure that the benefits of technology are fully realized. She holds master's degrees in information science and business administration from North Carolina Central University in Durham.

Named in honor of A. R. Zipf, a pioneer in information management systems, the \$10,000 fellowship is awarded annually to a student who is enrolled in graduate school in the early stages of study and shows exceptional promise for leadership and technical achievement in information management.

Listening to information specialists from around the world and learning about current practices at the IFLA meeting energized, inspired, and helped me develop a better appreciation for the profession.

—Khue Duong
Rovelstad Scholarship recipient 2008

CLIR CIOs Members (as of 9/15/08)

Christopher Barth, Luther College
 Param Bedi, Bucknell University
 Theresa Byrd, Ohio Wesleyan University
 Gai Carpenter, Hampshire College
 Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
 Jose Dieudonne, Arcadia University
 Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
 Charling Chang Fagan, Sarah Lawrence College
 Carol Falcione, Barnard College
 Cathy Fennell, Rosemont College
 Chris Ferguson, Pacific Lutheran University
 Megan Fitch, Beloit College
 Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
 Perry Hanson, Brandeis University
 W. Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
 Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
 Thomas Kirk, Earlham College
 Renee Jadushlever, Mills College
 Micheline Jedrey, Wellesley College
 Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
 Felice Maciejewski, Saint Norbert College
 Neil McElroy, Lafayette College
 Pamela McQuesten, Occidental College
 Terry Metz, Wheaton College
 Kathryn Monday, University of Richmond
 Charlotte Slocum Patriquin, Mount Holyoke College
 Rick Provine, DePauw University
 Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
 Suzanne Risley, Mitchell College
 Mike Roy, Middlebury College
 Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
 Elliott Shore, Bryn Mawr College
 Carol Smith, DePauw University
 Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
 Gene Wiemers, Bates College
 Frank Wojcik, SUNY College at Brockport

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Khue Duong, a master's degree candidate in the Information School at the University of Washington, was named the sixth recipient of the Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship. The award provides travel funds for a student of library and information science to attend the annual meeting of the World Library and Information Congress. Duong's interest in international librarianship stems from his conviction that information issues "transcend cultural differences, geographical borders, and governmental policies." Duong has a bachelor of science degree in chemistry and English from the University of California, Los Angeles, and a master's degree in linguistics from the University of California, Santa Cruz.

Survey of Graduate Information Programs and Accreditation

In 2008, CLIR partnered with the Information Professionals Task Force of the American Society for Information Science and Technology (ASIS&T) to examine the status of information professional programs and related accreditation activities. With funds from CLIR, ASIS&T commissioned Samantha Becker and Bo Kinney, graduate students at the University of Washington's Information School, to conduct a preliminary analysis of accreditation programs training information professionals. The report, *Graduate Information Programs and Accreditation: Landscape Analysis and Survey*, was released in June 2008 and is available at <http://www.asis.org/news.html>.

The report served as the basis for a September meeting at which representatives of information organizations discussed the establishment of a new accreditation process for the range of master's degree programs that educate information professionals.

Distinguished Presidential Fellows

Michael Keller, university librarian at Stanford University, director of Academic Information Resources, publisher of HighWire Press, and publisher of the Stanford University Press, continued in his role of CLIR Distinguished Presidential Fellow. Keller is engaged in research pertaining to cyberinfrastructure and ways our communities can respond to complex new environments that often include institutional repositories, digital archives, and digital libraries. In addition, he is working on a series of essays that are specific to rethinking aspects of libraries and academic life: the role of libraries and librarians, including facilities planning, position descriptions, implications for library and information schools, and longer-term implications for scholarship, teaching, and current academic organizational models.

In November 2007, Elliott Shore, Chief Information Officer at Bryn Mawr College, was appointed CLIR Distinguished Fellow for Leadership Programs. In this capacity, he continues to serve as dean of the Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries for Humanists while also working with CLIR President Charles Henry to design new leadership programs that support the development of digital scholarship.

CLIR Sponsors' Symposium

On December 12, 2007, CLIR hosted its eighth annual Sponsors' Symposium, titled "The Architecture of Knowledge: How Research Programs and New Courses Are Built." During the event, prominent faculty discussed a variety of resources and methods that can be used to conduct original research and to develop new perspectives through teaching. Christiane Gruber, art historian at Indiana University, discussed her research on Islamic manuscripts, and the social and communication skills necessary for accessing them. Stephen Nichols, professor of French at Johns Hopkins University and CLIR Board member, talked about digital humanities research, with focus on the *Roman de la Rose* project and how large digital manuscript collections can enrich research and teaching. Nancy Foster, lead anthropologist for the University of Rochester's River Campus Libraries and comanager of the libraries' digital initiatives unit, offered an anthropologist's approach to understanding the patterns and behaviors of researchers and students. Donald Waters, program officer for scholarly communication at The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, described the foundation's funding patterns over the past decade.

ADVISORY GROUPS

AS OF JUNE 30, 2008

Hidden Collections Review Panel

R. Howard Bloch
Yale University

Jacqueline Goldsby
University of Chicago

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Linda J. Colley
Princeton University

Charles Henry
CLIR

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Amy Friedlander
CLIR

Geneva Henry
Rice University

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Joan Giesecke
University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Michael Keller
Stanford University

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

Tyrone Cannon
University of San Francisco

Sam Demas
Carleton College

Joanne Schneider
Colgate University

Lynn Scott Cochrane
Denison University

Connie Vinita Dowell, *Chair*
San Diego State University

A. R. Zipf Fellowship Selection Committee

Miles Efron
University of Texas, Austin

Deanna B. Marcum, *Chair*
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
CLIR

Rena Zipf

Mellon Fellowships Selection Committee 2008

David Armitage
Harvard University

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
CLIR

Frederick Colby
Miami University

Brenda Foley
Marlboro College

Caroline Levander
Rice University

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN FY 2008

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
ASIS&T Silver Spring, MD	To gather data and perform a preliminary analysis related to the accreditation of programs for training information professionals	1/15/2008	\$5,000
Babeu, Alison Medford, MA	To serve as rapporteur at the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/2008	\$500
Brooks, Connie San Marcos, TX	To serve as expert consultant to advise on the development of CLIR's preservation agenda	8/1/2006	\$24,700
Columbia University New York, NY	To write an analysis of copyright with respect to recorded sound	4/2/2007	\$4,500
Courant, Paul Ann Arbor, MI	To study the cost of accessing and storing printed volumes in academic libraries	6/19/2008	\$4,000
Crane, Gregory Medford, MA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/2008	\$1,500
Douglas Oard College Park, MD	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/2008	\$1,500
Eakin, Lori Hillsborough, NC	To support the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economic Sustainability	1/22/2008	\$20,000
Foster, Nancy Rochester, NY	To facilitate a workshop on the study of faculty research behavior and its implications for the library at Cornell University	10/2/2007	\$2,000
Foster, Nancy Rochester, NY	To facilitate a workshop on the study of faculty research behavior and its implications for the library at the University of California, Berkeley	1/3/2008	\$4,500
Foster, Nancy Rochester, NY	To facilitate a workshop on the study of faculty research behavior and its implications for the library at George Washington University	2/21/2008	\$4,500
Gevinson, Alan Baltimore, MD	To perform a systematic examination of the results of several of the biggest mass digitization projects affecting materials of interest to scholars	8/10/2007	\$8,000
Huberman, Bernardo Palo Alto, CA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/2008	\$1,500
IATH Charlottesville, VA	To perform a systematic examination of the results of several of the biggest mass digitization projects affecting materials of interest to scholars	8/10/2007	\$8,000
Kanazawa Institute of Technology Library Center, Japan	To host the KIT/CLIR International Roundtable for Library and Information Science	9/1/2002	\$15,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Levander, Caroline Houston, TX	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/2008	\$1,500
Mosbo, Julie Austin, TX	To develop a database of international preservation activity	5/10/2007	\$3,000
Murray, Stephen South Salem, NY	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/2008	\$1,500
Nguyen, Lilly Los Angeles, CA	To perform a preliminary evaluation of tools to support digital humanities research	10/8/2007	\$5,000
Rentfrow, Daphnée Providence, RI	To assist with the CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship in Scholarly Information Resources Program	7/19/2007	\$5,000
Rieger, Oya Ithaca, NY	To write a white paper on the impacts of mass digitization	6/4/2007	\$5,000
Schiefsky, Mark Cambridge, MA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	4/3/2008	\$1,500
Schmitz, Dawn Las Vegas, NV	To write a report that relates user studies to the literature on the planning of cyberinfrastructure initiatives	8/29/2007	\$9,080
Schmitz, Dawn Las Vegas, NV	To perform a systematic examination of the results of several of the biggest mass digitization projects affecting materials of interest to scholars	8/10/2007	\$8,000
Shenker, Noah Los Angeles, CA	To support research as Distinguished Dissertation Fellow	5/24/2007	\$5,000
Shilton, Katie Los Angeles, CA	To perform a preliminary evaluation of tools to support digital humanities research	10/8/2007	\$5,000
Spiro, Lisa Houston, TX	To perform an analysis of platforms that could be used for the Hidden Collections project	5/7/2008	\$5,000
Stinson, Tim Baltimore, MD	To write a report on the meetings of the IMLS Postdoc Planning Grant group	12/6/2007	\$2,000
Stone, Maureen Woodinville, WA	To write a white paper as background for the CLIR/NEH symposium on promoting digital scholarship in the humanities	3/12/2008	\$1,500
University of Minnesota Minneapolis, MN	To develop EthicShare, a collaborative virtual community for ethicists	12/19/06	\$144,450
University of Virginia Charlottesville, VA	To support activities related to the Scholarly Communication Institute	12/19/06	\$25,000
Zorich, Diane Princeton, NJ	To perform a survey of American-based digital humanities centers	5/24/2007	\$63,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2008

WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a nonprofit organization) as of June 30, 2008, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources' management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2008, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 10 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
October 28, 2008

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2008

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2008</u>
Assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 2,278,020	\$ 4,217,199	\$ 6,495,219
Investments	-	2,613,091	2,613,091
Accounts receivable	99,954	-	99,954
Furniture and equipment, net	23,826	-	23,826
Other assets	<u>47,245</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>47,245</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 2,449,045</u>	<u>\$ 6,830,290</u>	<u>\$ 9,279,335</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 258,852	\$ -	\$ 258,852
Accrued expenses	<u>69,102</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>69,102</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 327,954</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 327,954</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 2,121,091</u>	<u>\$ 6,830,290</u>	<u>\$ 8,951,381</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 2,449,045</u>	<u>\$ 6,830,290</u>	<u>\$ 9,279,335</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2008

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2008</u>
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 140,515	\$ 5,693,725	\$ 5,834,240
Contributions	589,459	-	589,459
Publication sales	3,275	-	3,275
Investment income	36,870	90,611	127,481
Other income	<u>244,955</u>	<u>97,415</u>	<u>342,370</u>
	<u>\$ 1,015,074</u>	<u>\$ 5,881,751</u>	<u>\$ 6,896,825</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 608,180</u>	<u>\$ (608,180)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 1,623,254</u>	<u>\$ 5,273,571</u>	<u>\$ 6,896,825</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation	\$ 633,839	\$ -	\$ 633,839
Leadership	516,961	-	516,961
Other	19,960	-	19,960
Cyberinfrastructure	194,063	-	194,063
The next scholar	<u>287,280</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>287,280</u>
Total Program services	\$ 1,652,103	\$ -	\$ 1,652,103
Administration	<u>1,108,161</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>1,108,161</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 2,760,264</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 2,760,264</u>
Change in Net Assets	\$ (1,137,010)	\$ 5,273,571	\$ 4,136,561
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 3,258,101</u>	<u>\$ 1,556,719</u>	<u>\$ 4,814,820</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 2,121,091</u>	<u>\$ 6,830,290</u>	<u>\$ 8,951,381</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2008

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 4,136,561
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities	
Depreciation	11,285
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	102,227
Realized (gain)loss on investments	(28,025)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	(14,300)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	232,909
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>157,185</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	<u>\$ 4,597,842</u>
Investing Activities	
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 8,710,716
Purchases of investments	(8,190,148)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(16,063)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	<u>\$ 504,505</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ 5,102,347
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>1,392,872</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	<u>\$ 6,495,219</u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information	
Interest paid during the year	<u>\$ 661</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2008

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council on Library and Information Resources receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsorship revenues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2008
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2008 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

NOTE 2 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 193,296
Leasehold improvements	<u>4,015</u>
	197,311
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(173,485)</u>
	<u>\$ 23,826</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2008

(Continued)

NOTE 3- Investments – The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, “Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations.” Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2008

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Accrued interest			\$ 16,192
Stocks	\$ 28,025	\$ (20,360)	959,385
Bonds	-	1,409	70,012
Corporate fixed income	-	(3,436)	387,701
Government securities	-	18,318	681,838
Mutual funds	-	(98,158)	497,963
Subtotal	<u>\$ 28,025</u>	<u>\$ (102,227)</u>	<u>\$ 2,613,091</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	-	-	\$ 6,435,234
Total	<u>\$ 28,025</u>	<u>\$ (102,227)</u>	

NOTE 4 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program (“the Plan”) administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees’ salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$106,891 in 2008.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2008
(Continued)

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2008, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$2,613,091 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2008 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$6,435,234. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$5,665,520 from one organization which represents 82 % of total revenue.

NOTE 8 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, <u>2008</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 43,713
30 - 60 days	-
60 - 90 days	4,991
Over 90 days	51,250
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
 Total Accounts Receivable	 \$ <u>99,954</u>

NOTE 9 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August 2008. On October 13, 2008 The Council on Library and Information Resources entered into a new noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires February 28, 2010. The Council on Library and Information Resources subleases part of its space to the Digital Library Federation. Rental expense, net of sublease income for the year ending June 30, 2008 was \$167,974. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in June 1, 2010. Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30,</u>	<u>Capital Lease</u>	<u>Operating Leases</u>
2009	3,588	189,323
2010	3,588	211,671
2011	<u>-</u>	<u>63,407</u>
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 7,176	\$ <u>464,401</u>
Less: Amount representing interest.	<u>(674)</u>	
Present value of net minimum lease payments	\$ <u>6,502</u>	

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2008
(Concluded)

NOTE 10- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 11 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

- Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.
- Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.
- Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

A comparison of the carrying value of those financial instruments is as follows:

<u>June 30,</u> 2008	<u>Carrying</u> <u>Value</u>	<u>Fair</u> <u>Value</u>
Assets		
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 6,495,219	\$ 6,495,219
Accounts receivables-net(trade)	99,954	99,954
Liabilities		
Capital lease payable	6,502	6,502

NOTE 12 - Related Party

The Council on Library and Information Resources shares space with the Digital Library Federation. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for use of space and utilities. The Digital Library Federation paid The Council on Library and Information Resources \$12,000 for the use of space and utilities for the year ended June 30, 2008. The Council on Library and Information Resources has also entered into contracts with clients and has subcontracted with the Digital Library Federation to perform the work. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for any expenses paid by the Council on Library and Information Resources on their behalf.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2008

	The Next Scholar	Cyberinfrastructure	Leadership	Preservation	Other	Total Program Services	Admin.	Total 2008
Employee costs	\$ 22,553	\$ 32,025	\$ 566	\$ 525,754	\$ -	\$ 580,898	\$ 446,478	\$ 1,027,376
Professional services	216,685	98,182	63,659	32,595	16,033	427,155	178,694	605,849
Communications	25,207	236	457	41,004	232	67,136	38,597	105,733
Travel and meetings	22,812	29,141	437,599	29,457	3,622	522,631	126,326	648,957
Publications	11	4,830	14,630	4,926	-	24,397	9,185	33,582
Office operations	12	29,649	50	102	73	29,886	308,881	338,767
TOTAL	\$ <u>287,280</u>	\$ <u>194,063</u>	\$ <u>516,961</u>	\$ <u>633,839</u>	\$ <u>19,960</u>	\$ <u>1,652,103</u>	\$ <u>1,108,161</u>	\$ <u>2,760,264</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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